

PLURAL FORM IN ARABIC

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Annotation: this article deals with the construction of the plural format in Arabic and shows the construction and use of the plural based on examples.

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There are 2 types of plurals in Arabic:

1. broken plural - جَمْعُ تَكْسِيرٍ
2. correct plural - جَمْعُ سَالِمٍ

The broken plural is formed by breaking the singular form of the word. The singular form can be converted into a broken plural in 3 different ways:

1. By changing only the movement of the letters that come together. Example: أُسَدٌ - أُسَدٌ
2. By deleting one of the letters that come together. Example: كِتَابٌ - كُتُبٌ
3. By adding another letter to the unit. Example: قَلَمٌ - أَقْلَامٌ

The plural formed as a result of the change of vowels between the consonants that make up the core of the word, the introduction of non-consonant consonants, the change of the internal composition of the word, in other words, the change of the weight of the word is called broken plural¹. Example:

كُتُبٌ - كِتَابٌ - books, أُنْسَانٌ - إِنْسَانٌ - people.

¹ IbrohimovN., YusupovM. Arab tili grammatikasi 1. Namangan, 2009

A broken plural is formed from each word with its own weight. These weights are quite large and cannot be arranged according to a certain rule. A plural of a word with the same weight in a singular number can have a plurality of words with different weights with the same weight².

There are many words in the broken plural in the Holy Qur'an. We have started to study a part of them, that is, the 30th prayer, as far as Allah is able, may He give us encouragement in the path of knowledge, may He accept it as a prayer, my God.

We can see the places of broken plural in the Holy Qur'an from examples.

فِعَالٌ the weight is calculated from the most common weights.

In verse 7 of Surah Naba' ((وَ الْجِبَالِ أَوْ تَادًا)) فِعَالٌ in the weights(form) الْجِبَالُ (mountains)

the word comes. Singular form can be seen as جَبَلٌ weights فَعَلٌ (mountain).

In verse 6 of Surah Takvir, the word ((وَ إِذَا الْبِحَارُ سُجِّرَتْ)) فِعَالٌ (seas) appears in the weight of الْبِحَارُ The unit is فَعَلٌ in the weights بَحْرٌ (sea). There are also plural variants of the sea word أَبْحَارٌ بُحُورٌ أَبْحُرٌ . A question arises as to why exactly the word بَحْرٌ appears in the Holy Qur'an.

In verse 8th of Surah Fajr, the word ((الَّتِي لَمْ يُخْلَقْ مِثْلُهَا فِي الْبِلَادِ)) فِعَالٌ comes as verb بَلَدٌ (countries) appeared. The unit of active weight is فَعَلٌ as بِلَادٌ (countries) appeared. There is also a plural variant of the word land.

! Some weights are the same in the plural but have different weights in the singular. بُلْدَانٌ .

أَفْعَالٌ weight is also one of the most common weights.

In the 32nd verse of Surah Naba' ((حَدَائِقَ وَ أَعْنَابًا)) أَفْعَالٌ word أَعْنَابًا comes the word (vineyards).

In the 12th verse of Surah Infitor, ((إِنَّ الْأَبْرَارَ لَفِي نَعِيمٍ)) أَفْعَالٌ the word الْأَبْرَارَ (good ones) is appeared. Singular بَارٌّ (obedient, good). Also a good word بَرَّةٌ has also plural form.

² IbrohimovN., YusupovM. Arab tili grammatikasi1. Namangan, 2009

In the 13th verse of Surah ((وَ أَكْوَابُ مَوْضُوعَةٌ)) أَكْوَابُ word (goblets) appears. singular كُوبٌ

In the 9th verse of surah Fajr ((وَ فِرْعَوْنَ ذِي الْأَوْتَادِ)) أَفْعَالُ words الْأَوْتَادِ (soldiers) appears.

In the 18th verse of surah Balad ((أُولَئِكَ أَصْحَابُ الْمَيْمَنَةِ)) أَفْعَالُ words (owners) appears. Singular فَاعِلٌ is in the weights صَاحِبٌ. For this reason the word owners صَحْبٌ صَحْبٌ can be seen as a plural form.

In the 8th verse of surah Bayyina ((جَزَاؤُهُمْ عِنْدَ رَبِّهِمْ جَنَاتٌ عَدْنٍ تَجْرِي مِنْ تَحْتِهَا الْأَنْهَارُ)) أَفْعَالُ words الْأَنْهَارُ (rivers) appears. Singular فَعْلٌ word نَهْرٌ (river). There is plural form of this word نُهُورٌ أَنهْرٌ

In the 2nd verse of surah Zalzalā ((وَ أَخْرَجَتِ الْأَرْضُ أَثْقَالَ)) أَفْعَالُ word أَثْقَالٌ (luggages) appears. Singular فَعَالَةٌ word ثِقَالَةٌ (luggage).

In the 6th verse of surah Zalzalā ((يَوْمَئِذٍ يَصْدُرُ النَّاسُ أَشْتَاتًا لِيُرَوْا أَعْمَالَهُمْ)) أَفْعَالُ word أَعْمَالٌ (actions) appears. Singular can be as فَعْلٌ word عَمَلٌ (action).

! Some plural words do not have a singular form. It is not possible to weight the words in individual units. We can only learn all this by reading and memorizing. فَعْلٌ weight is one of the most common weights.

In the verse 13th surah Abasa ((فِي صُحُفٍ مُكَرَّمَةٍ)) فُعْلٌ word صُحُفٌ (pages) appears. Singular form فَعِيلَةٌ word صَحِيفَةٌ (page). There is also plural form صَحَافَاتٌ صَحَائِفٌ .

In verse 10 of Surah Takvir, verse 18 of Surah A'laa, and verse 2 of Surah Bayyina, فُعْلٌ word صُحُفٌ (pages) is appeared. Singular form فَعِيلَةٌ word صَحِيفَةٌ (page) .

In the 13th verse of Surah Ghashiya ((فِيهَا سُرُرٌ مَرْفُوعَةٌ)) فُعْلٌ word سُرُرٌ (So'rilar) word comes. Singular form فَعِيلٌ word سَرِيرٌ (so'ri). There is also plural form as أُسْرَةٌ .

In the verse of Bayyina ((فِيهَا كُتِبَ قِيمَةٌ)) word كُتِبَ (writings) appears. Singular form كِتَابَةٌ word كِتَابَةٌ (writing). كِتَابَاتٌ is plural form.

فُعُولٌ word is one of the most common weights.

In verse 8 of Surah Nazi'at ((قُلُوبٌ يَوْمَئِذٍ وَاجِفَةٌ)) word فُعُولٌ (қалблар) is appeared. Singular form فَعْلٌ is as this word قَلْبٌ (soul) .

In the verse 38 of Surah Abasa ((وَجُوهٌ يَوْمَئِذٍ مُّسْفِرَةٌ)) word فُعُولٌ (faces)is appeared. Singular form فَعْلٌ word وَجْهٌ (face) . There is also plural form as أَوْجُهُ.

In the verse of 2nd of Surah Takweer ((وَ إِذَا النُّجُومُ انْكَدَرَتْ)) word فُعُولٌ النُّجُومُ (stars) is appeared. Singular form فَعْلٌ word نَجْمٌ (star) .

In verse 5th of Surah Takweer ((وَ إِذَا الْوُحُوشُ حُشِرَتْ)) word فُعُولٌ الْوُحُوشُ (wild animals) appears. Singular form فَعْلٌ word وَحْشٌ (wild animal) .

In verse 7th of Surah Takweer ((وَ إِذَا النُّفُوسُ زُوِّجَتْ)) word فُعُولٌ in the weight النَّفُوسُ comes the word (needs). Singular form فَعْلٌ word نَفْسٌ (need) . there is also plural form as أَنْفُوسٌ .

In the verse 4th of Surah Intifor ((وَ إِذَا الْقُبُورُ بُعْثِرَتْ)) word فُعُولٌ الْقُبُورُ (souls) appears. Singular form فَعْلٌ word قَبْرٌ (soul).

In the 1st verse of Surah Burudj ((وَ السَّمَاءِ ذَاتِ الْبُرُوجِ)) word فُعُولٌ الْبُرُوجِ (constellations) comes. Singular form فَعْلٌ word بُرْجٌ (constellation) . There is also plural form as أَبْرَاجٌ .

In the 17th verse of Surah Burudj ((هَلْ أَتَاكَ حَدِيثُ الْجُنُودِ)) word فُعُولٌ الْجُنُودِ (soldiers) appears. Singular form فَعْلٌ word جُنْدٌ (soldier) . There is also plural form as أَجْنَادٌ .

In the verse of Surah Goshiya ((وَجُوهٌ يَوْمَئِذٍ خَاشِعَةٌ)) word فُعُولٌ (faces) appears. Singular form فَعْلٌ word وَجْهٌ (face).

In the 9th verse of Surah Aadiyat ((أَفَلَا يَعْلَمُ إِذَا بُعْثِرَ مَا فِي الْقُبُورِ)) word فُعُولٌ الْقُبُورِ (souls) appears. Singular form فَعْلٌ word قَبْرٌ (soul) .

In the 10th verse of Surah Aadiyat ((وَ حُصِّلَ مَا فِي الصُّدُورِ)) word فُعُولُ (souls) appears. Singular form فَعْلٌ word صَدْرٌ (soul).

In the 5th verse of Surah Naas ((الَّذِي يُوسُّوسُ فِي صُدُورِ النَّاسِ)) word فُعُولُ (souls) appears. Singular فَعْلٌ word صَدْرٌ (soul).

فَعَائِلٌ weight is one of the most common weights.

In the 33rd verse of Surah Nabaa ((وَ كَوَاعِبُ أَنْثَابًا)) فَعَائِلٌ word كَوَاعِبُ (girls) appears. Singular form فَاعِلٌ word كَاعِبٌ (girl).

In the 2nd verse of Surah Infitor ((وَ إِذَا الْكُوَاكِبُ انْتَبَرَتْ)) فَعَائِلٌ word الْكُوَاكِبُ (stars) appears. Singular form فَعْلٌ word كَوْكَبٌ (star) .

In the 9th verse of Surah Toriq ((يَوْمَ تُبْلَى السَّرَائِرُ)) فَعَائِلٌ word السَّرَائِرُ (secrets) appears. Singular فَعْلٌ word سِرٌّ (secret) .

فُعْلٌ weight is one of the most common weights.

In the 4th verse of Surah Falak ((وَ مِنْ شَرِّ النَّفَّاثَاتِ فِي الْعُقَدِ)) فُعْلٌ word الْعُقَدِ (nodes) word comes. Singular form فُعْلَةٌ word عُقْدَةٌ (node).

In conclusion, the Arabic language is distinguished from other languages by its subtlety, by changing the meaning of the whole letter with the exchange of a single letter or action. Its beauty, meaningfulness, strict rules and exceptions increase the pleasure of the learner. As you learn, you will find miracles in it... Arabic language is valuable and interesting to us because it is primarily the language of the divine Word.

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